

FRAMEWORK FOR DURABILITY ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES IN THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY

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Keywords: Continuous fibre composite, Analysis framework, Finite element, Global - Local

ABSTRACT

High performance composite materials possess properties that make them great candidates for reducing the weight of cars. However, analysis of large structures or assemblies with complex geometries made from fibre reinforced composite materials is a difficult task. Modern state of the art set of failure initiation criteria are based on the full stress state while efficient standard shell models cannot provide this. This either requires high fidelity models or the risk that potentially critical failure modes may be neglected due to assumptions made in the numerical models.

In this paper, a framework for computationally efficient durability analysis of composite structures in automotive industry is presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry faces an outstanding challenge to reduce the environmental impact due to car transportation. Car transportation is responsible for 17.5% of the greenhouse gas emissions in Sweden [1] and 12% of the total CO₂-emissions in Europe. With current legislation within the European Union [2_Thesis], shown in Figure 1, an upper limit of 70 g CO₂ / km is in place for 2025 compared to 130 g CO₂ / km in 2015 [2]. During the UN climate summit in 2018, future reductions for EU by 37.5% from 2021 levels to 2030 were agreed upon [3].

High performance composite materials, with their superior specific properties are an outstanding alternative to add lightness to car structures. Even if the price for such materials initially are higher compared to traditional engineering materials but still are beneficial for both € per saved weight [4] and from an LCA perspective [5], there are also engineering challenges. One major roadblock for higher utilisation of composite materials and their superior properties in more industries than aerospace is the lack of efficient and accurate analysis methods that do not rely on extensive test campaigns to demonstrate a safe design [6].

In this contribution we present an analysis framework for performing efficient analysis of large complex automotive composite structures from a durability perspective. The framework handles high performing continuous composite materials with orthotropic properties, e.g. Non-Crimp Fabric reinforced materials [7,8]. First the key parts of failure prediction in orthotropic materials and evaluation of composite structures in large assemblies are discussed. Then these parts are fitted into a framework for efficient analysis in commercial software well known in automotive industry.

2 CHALLENGES WITH ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS IN AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY

High performing composite materials have been used within other industry sectors, e.g. aerospace industry and car racing, for about half a century [9,10]. Both aerospace industry and car racing have

relied heavily on physical testing to ensure and show the structural integrity for such parts and assemblies. The incentive to reduce weight to increase the performance is so high in these industries that these large test campaigns have been motivated. Due to the high cost and long lead times that are associated with physical testing, such an approach is just not feasible for automotive industry.

Moreover, design philosophies and design guidelines differ between aerospace industry and automotive industry. Looking at the complex shape of an automotive body structure with a high degree of integration of parts, subjected to complex loads causes complex stress states. For isotropic materials, i.e. metals, these complex stress states are not necessarily a problem as out-of-plane stress components still are small compared to the allowable stress. However, for composite materials, high out-of-plane stresses caused by bending and twisting of curved geometries can be detrimental. This as the out-of-plane strength for composite materials can be one or two orders of magnitude lower compared to in-plane allowable stresses.

Automotive industry relies heavily on Computer Aided Engineering (CAE) tools for assessment of the design throughout the design cycles. Therefore there is a demand for CAE tools that can capture all relevant failure modes in structural parts made from composite materials in an efficient and robust manner. An important aspect is to have the tools and processes integrated into commercial software and preferable software that is already known to the automotive industry.

In addition, design guidelines that are based on experimental results for specific geometries and constraints on the laminate design are often limited to the tested material system. As new composite materials are developed or improved, a framework that relies on very few material tests is of great advantage. Constraints on laminate design, e.g. amount of fibres in different direction can allow for easier prediction of failure as some failure modes can be suppressed, however, this might lead to designs that have com

3 ANALYSIS FRAME WORK

In this work, this procedure for an analysis frame work is outlined using Abaqus [11] as the FE solver and Ansa [12] and Metapost [13] from Beta CAE as the pre- and post-processors. These are software that is already used in automotive industry. For functionality that presently are lacking in these tools, Matlab and Fortran routines are developed to be used within the frame work.

The proposed analysis framework is outlined in Figure 1 and described more in detail in the articles by Molker et al. [14,15]. The first part concerns screening of the structure for potential hot spots. In the second part, detailed models of these locations are created using a model of higher fidelity than that used in the global analysis. The third part is a post-processing step to ease analysis of the results from the higher fidelity model to evaluate the design.

The different parts are visualized in Figure 2 for a test specimen for measurement of tensile out-of-plane normal strength [16]. In the first part, critical locations are found based on failure index above a certain threshold, predicted with a stress based state of the art set of failure initiation criteria. Based on the location of predicted hot spots, local submodels are built in the second part. With information from the global model, and information about the geometry and layup from the database used for creating the global model, new detailed models are created with standard pre-processing tools, e.g. geometric boolean operations, batchmeshing and volumisation of shells.

The different key parts marked with thick red borders in Figure 1 in the framework are described in the following chapters. The other parts are parts are based on tools that are already available in commercial tools. However, the different parts are pieces that are needed to be able to efficiently address failure initiation in automotive structures made of reinforced composite materials with orthotropic properties. Having the different pieces is not enough, one just as important thing is to place these pieces into a logical procedure that can be automated. This to reduce the input needed from a stress engineer to as few tasks as possible for model building and free as much time as possible for analyses of the results.

Figure 1: Outlined framework for efficient analysis of composite automotive structures. The three main parts are divided into tasks. Task marked with a grey box is performed outside of commercial tools and tasks marked in bright red need manual interaction to some extent.

Figure 2: Illustration of the parts of the Framework. In Part 1, hot spots are identified and visualised in the global model. In Part 2, the identified and selected hot spot locations are remodelled using volumisation of a refined shell mesh of the area. The local model is then solved using submodelling in Abaqus. In Part 3, the solved submodels are postprocessed together with the global model.

4 PREDICTION OF FAILURE INITIATION IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Being able to accurately predict failure in large models subjected to multiple load cases is of uttermost importance without the need for extensive test campaigns. The accuracy of failure predictions in fibre reinforced polymers has improved over the last decades. This is especially true since the introduction of physically based failure initiation criteria, e.g. Hashin [17], Puck [18] and LaRC05 [19], over polynomial base, e.g. Tsai-Hill [20] and Tsai-Wu [21], and limit criteria, e.g. max stress or max strain. It is of great importance to be able to do this accurately in both global and local models within the proposed framework.

4.1 Failure in reinforced polymers with orthotropic properties

Physically based failure criterion for initiation are developed for unidirection reinforcement, e.g. tape based reinforcement, which are transversally isotropic. Other reinforcement, as weave or non-crimp fabrics (NCF) are often treated as layered unidirectional materials. Studied have found that at least NCF reinforced materials are orthotropic at least when it comes to strength with lower allowable strength in the out-of-plane direction compared to the in-plane direction.

The lower out-of-plane tensile strength in NCF reinforced materials, is accounted for in an extended set of failure initiation criteria of LaRC05, denoted LaRC05NCF [22]. The following five failure modes are addressed for first ply failure, Matrix failure (tensile or compressive), Fibre tensile failure and Fibre compressive failure (fibre kinking or fibre splitting), see Figure 3. All failure modes are evaluated based on the 3D stress state and for a number of assumed critical fracture planes.

Figure 3: Intralaminar failure modes in LaRC05 and the stress state that is evaluated. (a) matrix failure in tension and (b) in compression, (c) fibre tensile failure, (d) fibre compressive failure – fibre kinking and (e) fibre compressive failure – fibre splitting.

Matrix related failure in the transverse direction, illustrated in Figure 3 (d) for tensile loading and Figure 3 (e) for compressive loading, is governed by the properties of the matrix material. Both tensile and compressive matrix failure index (FI) are combined to one criterion for matrix related failure FI_M as found in LaRC05 [19]:

$$FI_M = \left(\frac{\tau_T}{S_T^{is} - \eta_T \sigma_N} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_L}{S_L^{is} - \eta_L \sigma_L} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_N \rangle_+}{Y_T^{is}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

where $\langle \rangle_+$ denotes the McCauley bracket and differentiate between tensile and compressive normal stress on the fracture plane. The tractions on a potential fracture plane, τ_T , τ_L and σ_N are compared to the allowable S_T^{is} , S_L^{is} and Y_T^{is} taking in-situ effects into account [19]. Friction stress from the micro-cracks on the fracture plane is calculated from the normal stress, σ_N , and a friction coefficient in the transverse, η_T , and longitudinal directions, η_L .

Fibre tensile failure, shown in Figure 3 (a), is governed by the strength of the fibres and the stress in the fibre direction, σ_{11} . The failure index for fibre tensile failure FI_{FT} is evaluated according to the criterion:

$$FI_{FT} = \frac{\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle_+}{X_T} = 1 \quad (2)$$

where X_T is the strength measured in the 1-direction.

Fibre compressive failure exhibits two different failure modes, *fibre kinking*, illustrated in Figure 3 (b) and *fibre splitting*, illustrated in Figure 3 (c). These are in fact matrix controlled failure modes and occurs at a misaligned fracture plane denoted with superscript ‘‘m’’. The criterion for fibre kinking FI_{KINK} and FI_{SPLITT} is evaluated in LaRC05 [19] as:

$$FI_{KINK|SPLITT} = \left(\frac{\tau_{23}^m}{S_T^{is} - \eta_T \sigma_{22}^m} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}^m}{S_L^{is} - \eta_L \sigma_{22}^m} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{22}^m \rangle_+}{Y_T^{is}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (3)$$

The two failure modes are predicted with the same criterion, given in Equation 2. The distinction between fibre kinking and splitting according to Equation 3 is empirical in LaRC05 [19]. Fibre kinking and fibre splitting are distinguished with the magnitude of the fibre direction stress according to Equation 4:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Kinking if } \sigma_{11} &< -X_C/2 \\ \text{Splitting if } \sigma_{11} &\geq -X_C/2 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where σ_{11} is the stress in the fibre direction, and X_C is the measured compressive strength.

The most critical failure mode and failure index is then determined by the maximum of all calculated failure indices, given by Equation 5.

$$FI = \max(FI_M, FI_{FT}, FI_{KINK|SPLITT}) \quad (5)$$

LaRC05NCF [22] is used for orthotropic NCF reinforced composite materials. In addition to the failure modes in LaRC05 [19], a failure mode for interlaminar failure is evaluated and this is illustrated in Figure 4.

Interlaminar matrix failure is driven imperfections and defects between the fibre bundles in the normal direction in NCF reinforced composite materials [22]. For transverse failure in the out-of-plane direction that occurs within the matrix interface, (MI), the following criterion is used:

$$FI_{M,MI} = \left(\frac{\tau_{T,MI}}{S_T - \eta_T \sigma_N} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{L,MI}}{S_L - \eta_L \sigma_N} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{N,MI} \rangle_+}{Z_T} \right)^2 = 1, \text{ if } \sigma_N > 0 \quad (6)$$

where Z_T is the measured out-of-plane tensile strength. This is evaluated under pure tensile loading for a fracture plane $\alpha = 90^\circ$.

Figure 4: Transverse interlaminar matrix failure in orthotropic NCF reinforced composite materials.

4.2 Failure prediction in local detailed models

For local detailed models with layered reinforced composite materials it is common practice [ref] to build models with solid elements, and at least one solid element per layer to resolve the full 3D stress state.

The proposed set of failure initiation criteria in LaRC05NCF [22] is implemented as a user subroutine (UVARM) for Abaqus Standard [11]. The implementation calculates the current FI for each material point in the model for solid elements, e.g. Hexahedral (brick shaped) or Tetrahedral (C3D8 or C3D4 or C3D10) elements.

The implementation is verified on a corrugated specimen described in [23] where physical experiments are compared to numerical simulations with detailed solid FE models. For this purpose 20 mm long sections of the plate is used consisting of one crest and two bays, with a radius of 9.5 mm and approximately 40 mm wide, see Figure 5 (a). The specimens are made from the NCF material HTS45 fibres (Porcher, 205 g/m²) and LY556 (Huntsman) matrix. Both unidirectional specimens ([90]₁₆ lay-up), as well as a cross ply specimen ([90/0]_{4S} lay-up) are studied. The material data can be found in the article by Molker et al. [24].

Figure 5: (a) Geometry of test specimen. (b) Loading and constraints of the specimen. Side view along the length of the specimen and cross section of the specimen in the cross-section A-A.

The load case is designed to achieve a moment over the specimen that will open up the radius, see Figure 5 (b), thereby creating interlaminar tensile stresses within the specimen, similar to the ones in [13]. The setup is described in the article by Molker et al. [24].

The numerical models are analysed with implicit FE models in Abaqus Standard. The specimens are modelled with 48,000 solid second order hexahedral elements with one element over the thickness of each NCF ply. A biasing of the elements is done to increase the mesh density in the critical upper half. During the FE simulations the failure initiation is predicted with the UVARM subroutine.

The FE simulations with the implemented subroutine predicts out-of-plane failure triggered by large out-of-plane normal stresses, shown in Figure 6. These results were confirmed with the physical experiments. Moreover, FE-predictions with failure predictions based on transverse isotropy would not predict this as the critical failure mode, and thereby overestimate the strength of the specimens.

Figure 6: a) First ply failure location in the physical experiments. b) Failure initiation predictions from FE simulations.

4.3 Stress state prediction in large global models

As seen in Equation 1-3,5 for the proposed set of failure initiation criteria for orthotropic, as well as for transversely isotropic materials, the full 3D stress tensor is needed. Without this, potentially critical failure modes can be missed during assessment of a structure. As seen in previous section, solid models possess the possibility to accurately do this. However, due to the computational cost associated with such models, they cannot be used efficiently for large components or assemblies. In such models shell elements are used due to their efficiency.

Standard shell elements on the other hand are based on the assumption of a plane stress state [25,26]. Using these elements will simply disregard failure modes that are driven by out of plane stress components as illustrated in Figure 7. Here an analytical solution for the out-of-plane normal stress in a curved beam subjected to an opening bending moment is compared to predictions from a FE model with solid elements (C3D8 in Abaqus) and one with standard shell elements (S4R in Abaqus).

Figure 7: Normal out-of-plane stress prediction through the thickness of a curved beam subjected to an opening bending moment. Results are shown for the lower centre element that is highlighted. a) An analytical solution b) prediction with solid elements and c) prediction with standard shell elements. d) Prediction using the Extended 2D FEM approach described in Section 4.4.

If the stress state from such a model is to be used together with a failure initiation criteria based on the full 3D stress state, inaccurate predictions will be made. This is something that could lead to loss of the structural integrity with catastrophic failure as a consequence.

In literature different approaches for reconstructing the full stress state based on results from shell elements exist. One of these is the Extended 2D FEM approach presented by Rohwer et al. [27]. The advantage with this approach is that the full stress state can be predicted accurately for curved geometries based on only the element definition and nodal results. The results for the specimen in section 4.3 using the Extended 2D FEM approach is shown in Figure 7.

The additional cost of second order shell elements is a prerequisite. The Extended 2D FEM approach is studied by Molker et al. in [28], where the limitations in modelling requirements are studied for different geometries and laminate thicknesses. In this study it was found that geometries with high curvature and thick laminates can be modelled with good accuracy. Also integrated structures, e.g. a T-joint, where different skins are attached and modelled with tie-constraints [11] can be modelled with good accuracy.

The Extended 2D FEM approach is implemented in Metapost v20 for postprocessing Abaqus models built with second order shell elements [29].

4.4 Failure prediction in global models

With the possibility to accurately predict the full 3D stress state in global models, it is also possible to predict failure initiation according to a physically based set of failure criteria based on the stress state. In this work, this is done according to LaRC05NCF [22] using inhouse Matlab-code that calculates the failure index, fracture plane, critical ply and failure mode and then exports this to common post processors as HyperView or Metapost as ascii-files for efficient post processing. An example of this is shown in Figure 8 for the specimens used in section 4.3.

Figure 8: Failure prediction based on the full 3D stress state. a) Critical failure mode, b) Failure index, c) Critical ply and d) Fracture plane angle.

With these tools it is possible to find critical locations in global models analysed with efficient shell models. As the accuracy, from the stress prediction, is dependent on the geometry and element resolution, refined analyses of these hot spots could be needed. This can then be done using the information from the global model, to build detailed local models of only the critical locations. These small models can then be analysed using sub-modelling technique. This is a technique that is available in some commercial FE solvers, e.g. Abaqus [11] and Ansys [30].

5 APPLICATION TO AUTOMOTIVE PARTS

The proposed analysis frame work is utilised for an automotive structure found behind the rear row of seats in a saloon car, called the backplate. The component can be found in Figure 9 where the load case also is illustrated. The load case reassembles torsion/twisting of the car body together with a point load from a belt anchorage.

Figure 9: a) Location of the backplate in a car body. b) Global model of the backplate with an overall 3mm second order mesh with mainly quad elements.

The global model is built with $\sim 150'000$ shell elements, mainly second order quadrilaterals (S8R). The backplate is build with a unidirectional layup with AS4/3501-6 composite material [16,31] oriented along the main x -axis.

In this model, two hot spots are found as shown Figure 10 (a). One of these are determined to critical based on a Failure Index threshold of 0.3 as seen in Figure 10 (b). The threshold value needs to be determined based on factors as maturity of material data, geometrical complexity in combination with modelling resolution, etc. A high threshold value leads to few analysed hot spots, with risk of missing critical once, and a low value results in a high number of detailed analyses.

Figure 10: a) Result for the global model where the identified hot spots are shown with proposed volumes. b) Failure indices for the hot spots together with a threshold for what to model in detail.

The sub-model is created according to the process presented in section 3 and in [14,15]. The hot spot is analysed and the results are imported in the global model for common post-processing as shown in Figure 11 (a). A closer view of the detailed model is shown in Figure 11 (b). In this case, the predicted failure index by the global model agrees well to that predicted by the local model.

Figure 11: Hot spot 1 viewed from behind with the global model shell model and the detailed local model overlaid. The left half of the local model is masked to visualise the global model in that region.
(a) Global view and (b) zoomed in view at the hot spot.

6 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE OUTLOOK

The proposed framework for assessment of fibre reinforced composite structures significantly improves the analyses procedure for failure initiation. The proposed analysis frame work does not only allow for an efficient analysis of composite structures, but also for consistent results and conclusions as the analysis frame work is highly automated. The framework is integrated into commercial software commonly used within automotive industry. This includes all steps from model build through solving the FE-models to analysis and post-processing of results.

Using shell elements with shell section properties can allow for easier introduction of insitu strength [19] allowables. Both in the global model, but also in the local model. With knowledge about the layup and stacking sequence, automatic creation of different material cards and allowables could be defined when creating the volumised solid model.

A future development to the implemented Extended 2D FEM would be to allow for double-curved geometries and arbitrary shaped elements. The influence and modelling approaches needed to retain accurate enough stress prediction is of great importance for the general case.

In addition to the implementation of the Extended 2D FEM approach in Metapost, the addition of 3D stress based set of failure initiation criteria like Puck [18] or LaRC05NCF [22] would avoid the need for using external functions or software aside from commonly used solvers and pre- and post-processors.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work is funded through Volvo Car Industrial PhD program (VIPP) and the Swedish Research Council (VR) 2012-4320. Financial support from Vinnova, via LIGHTer Academy, is gratefully acknowledged.

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